

The Impact of Social Interaction for the Result of Social Subject Grade VII in UPTD SMP Negeri 1 Pematang Siantar

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to determine the "Influence of Social Interaction on Student Learning Outcomes in Social Sciences Subjects Class VIII UPTD SMP Negeri 1 Pematang Siantar". This type of research is quantitative research with a quantitative descriptive analysis approach. The research population was students at the UPTD SMP Negeri 1 Pematang Siantar school with a total of 187 students. The sampling technique used was the Slovin sampling technique. Data collection techniques use questionnaires, tests and documentation. The hypothesis generation technique uses simple linear regression analysis and the coefficient of determination (R^2). The results of the research show that: there is a positive and significant influence on social interaction on student learning outcomes. This result can be seen in the t test where the calculated t value of social interaction ($9.995 > t$ table value 2.6025) which means the variable is significant. The R Square coefficient of determination test was found to be 0.35, which means that 35% of social interaction variables influence student learning outcomes at the UPTD SMP Negeri 1 Pematang Siantar school. Meanwhile, 65% is the influence of other variables not examined in this research.

$Y : 10.127 + 0.778$

INTRODUCTION

Basically, humans are creatures who have the nature of being individuals and social creatures. As individuals, humans have their own potential and advantages. Meanwhile, as social creatures, humans have the ability to socialize or live together with other people. All human abilities, both intellectual abilities and social skills, need to be developed through a learning process so that they can play a role according to their function and purpose. This can be achieved through the educational process. From this it is clear that education is a necessity for humans.

Sardiman, (2007:95) said that in principle "learning is doing, doing means carrying out activities. So, learning activities are the process of students doing various things related to learning." In the learning process between educators and students there must be a process of social interaction that exists. As educators, you should be aware of what should be done to create a conducive learning environment for students to achieve the expected goals. The teacher's task as an educator is to try to create an exciting and enjoyable learning atmosphere for students. Teachers as educators not only dominate during the learning process, but also help in creating conducive conditions and provide motivation and guidance so that students can develop their potential and creativity, through teaching and learning interactions. Learning outcomes according to Amir & Risnawati (2015: 5-6) are "the abilities that children gain after going through learning activities". The aspects above are closely related to the other nature of humans, namely as social creatures. The nature of humans as social creatures means that humans cannot live without other humans. Based on observations made at UPTD SMP Negeri 1 Pematang Siantar, there are many students whose learning outcomes can still be said to be low. As researchers have experienced in schools, there are still many students who are less able to interact socially, both with the environment, each other and with their teachers.

Therefore, researchers are interested in conducting research with the title "The Influence Of Social Interaction On Student Learning Outcomes In The Subject Of Social Sciences Class Viii Uptd Smp Negeri 1 Pematang Siantar".

LITERATURE REVIEW

Social interaction is a process where relationships occur between individuals to individuals, individuals to groups and vice versa, and groups to groups in the community environment. Meanwhile, learning outcomes are the result of students' potential or abilities in the form of assessments given by educators after students have participated in the learning process. includes cognitive, affective and psychomotor skills. Therefore, in a learning process, social interaction at school plays a very important role as a driver of student learning outcomes. Without social interaction at school, the teaching and learning process will not achieve its maximum goals. Thus, if social interaction at school is implemented appropriately, students will have high learning outcomes in accordance with the expected goals.

Figure 2.1
conceptual framework

METHODS

This research uses quantitative research methods, which are aimed at explaining the influence of social interaction on student learning outcomes in social studies subjects for class VIII UPTD SMP Negeri 1 Pematang Siantar. The data analysis methods used are validity tests and reliability tests to measure the validity of the questionnaire and use the t test to determine statistical significance differences between the average value of a sample distribution and the population parameters and a determination test based on statistical tests using MS.Exel 2010.

The measurement scale used in this research is the Likert scale which is used to measure social interaction on student learning outcomes in social studies subjects class VIII UPTD SMP Negeri 1 Pematang Siantar. The population in this study were students in class VIII UPTD SMP Negeri 1 Pematang Siantar with a total of 348 students. and the sample was 187 students using the Slovin formula with a standard error of 0.05. Sampling used Simple Random Sampling.

This research is used to determine the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable, where in this research there is one independent variable (X), namely: Social Interaction, and Learning Outcomes (Y).

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Result

1. Normality Test

The normality test in this study used the Chi-square normality test. The test criteria are to compare $X_{hitung} < X_{tabel}$ and draw conclusions if $X_{hitung} < X_{tabel}$.

The results of the normality test in this study can be seen in the table below:

Table 4.1
Chi-Square Normality Test Results

Description	Social interaction	Learning outcomes
Average	47,687	55,500
Standard deviation	4,883	5,268
Amount of data	187	187
X_{hitung}	3.63	5.63
X_{tabel}	5,991	5,991
Conclusion	Normally Distributed Data	Normally Distributed Data

(Source: Data Processed by Microsoft Excel)

2. Product Moment Correlation Test

In this research, the product moment correlation test is used. The test criteria are that the calculated data is then consulted at r_{tabel} a significant rate of 5%, so that H_a it is accepted if $r_{hitung} > r_{tabel}$, if H_a it is accepted then there is an influence of social interaction on students' social studies learning outcomes. This formula will be assisted by using the Ms.Exel application.

The results of the product moment correlation test in this research can be seen in the table below:

Table 4. 2
Product Moment Correlation Test Results

N	Rxy	r _{table}
187	0.592	0.143

(Source: Data Processed by Microsoft Excel)

Based on the product moment correlation test table above, it shows that the data is $r_{hitung}(0.592) > r_{tabel}(0.143)$ and accepts H_a . So, there is an influence of social interaction on the learning outcomes of class VIII social studies students.

3. Simple Linear Regression Equation

Simple linear regression analysis is used to determine the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable. In this research, what needs to be seen is the influence of the independent variable consisting of the Social Interaction variable (X) on Learning Outcomes (Y). The results of the data using Microsoft Excel can be seen in the following table.

Table 4. 3
Simple Regression Analysis Results

	Coefficients	Standard Error	t Stat	P-value	Lower 95%	Upper 95%	Lower 95.0%	Upper 95.0%
Intercept	10.1278	3.8025	2,663	0.008	2,625	17,629	2,625	17,629
X1	0.7789	0.0779	9,995	0,000	0.625	0.9327	0.625	0.9327

(Source: Data Processed by Microsoft Excel)

Data analysis according to table 4.3 shows that this research obtained a constant value of 10.127, which means that if the Social Interaction value is 0 then the student learning outcome value is 10.127. The regression coefficient for the Social Interaction variable is 0.778, which means that every 1 unit increase in Social Interaction will be followed by student learning outcomes of 0.778 or 77%. The simple linear regression equation used is:

$$Y = a + bx$$

$$Y = 10.127 + 0.778x$$

This means that every student's social interaction has a positive effect on student learning outcomes of 10.127.

4. t Test (Partial)

t Test (Partial) used to determine the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable. In this research, what needs to be seen is the influence of the independent variable consisting of the Social Interaction variable (X) on Learning Outcomes (Y).

The results of the data using Microsoft Excel can be seen in the following table.

Table 4. 4
t Test Results (Partial)

	Coefficients	Standard Error	t Stat	P-value	Lower 95%	Upper 95%	Lower 95.0%	Upper 95.0%
Intercept	10.1278	3.8025	2,663	0.008	2,625	17,629	2,625	17,629
X1	0.7789	0.0779	9,995	0,000	0.625	0.9327	0.625	0.9327

(Source: Data Processed by Microsoft Excel)

Based on table 4.4, it is found that the calculated t value (9.995) is greater than the t table value (2.6025). This indicates that the research results reject H₀ and accept H₁. Thus, simultaneously the Social Interaction and Learning Outcomes of students at SMP Negeri 1 Pematang Siantar school have a significant level of influence. This means that the hypothesis which states that students' social interactions simultaneously influence student learning outcome variables at SMP Negeri 1 Pematang Siantar can be accepted.

Coefficient of Determination Test

The coefficient of determination test (R²) is used to measure the level of the model's ability to explain the dependent variable. The results of the data using Microsoft Excel can be seen in the following table :

Table 4.9

Coefficient of Determination Test Results

SUMMARY OUTPUTS

Regression Statistics	
Multiple R	0.592171
R Square	0.350667
Adjusted R Sq	0.347157
Standard Error:	3.416443
Observations	187

The coefficient of determination R Square value in table 4.4 is known to be 0.35. Which means 35% of the Social Interaction variable influences student learning outcomes at SMP Negeri 1 Pematang Siantar school. Meanwhile, 65% is the influence of other variables not examined in this research. The results of the analysis above have the implication that good student social interaction at school needs to be paid attention to in order to improve student learning outcomes at SMP Negeri 1 Pematang Siantar school. This is important to increase the contribution of the Social Interaction variable by 43%.

Discussion

Based on the statistical analysis that has been carried out on each research variable, the researcher tries to provide a discussion of the problems discussed in this research, namely: **The Influence of Social Interaction (X) on Student Learning Outcomes (Y) in Social Sciences Subjects Class VIII UPTD Public Middle Schools 1 Pematangsiantar.**

The test results show that partially Social Interaction (X) has a positive and significant effect on student learning outcomes as a variable (Y). This can be seen from the Social Interaction regression coefficient value (X) of 0.778 with a significance value of 0.049, so H₁ is accepted so that it can be concluded that Social Interaction has a positive and significant effect on Student Learning Outcomes in Class VIII Social Sciences subjects at UPTD SMP Negeri 1 Pematang Siantar.

In the output results above, a significant value = 0.049 < 0.05 is obtained. So it can be concluded that a teacher and student or student and student should have social interaction in understanding good teaching techniques in order to have an influence in improving student learning outcomes.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

Based on the research results and discussion in chapter IV, the conclusions that can be put forward in this research are as follows:

There is a positive and significant influence of 35% between social interactions on student learning outcomes in social studies subjects class VIII SMP Negeri 1 Pematang Siantar for the 2022/2023 academic year. This can be seen from the partial calculation results of the t test on the social interaction variable (X) carried out with the help of Microsoft.

Recommendation

From the results of research conducted by researchers, there are several suggestions that need to be considered for various parties in order to improve further research as well as the benefits of this research, namely:

1. For Researchers

It is hoped that this research can contribute to the development of knowledge about educational management through studying students' social interactions at school on learning outcomes, and can be used as a reference and consideration for further research.

2. For HKBP Nomensen University

This research can be used as reference or study material for other researchers, especially for students of economic education study programs.

3. For the next researcher

Due to the limitations in this research, it is hoped that future research will be more in-depth in exploring information and preparing instruments. So that more facts can be revealed that underlie students' social interactions on student learning outcomes.

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